

Service Quality, Creativity And Promotion Media Toward Visitor Satisfaction of (Farm House and The Great Asia Afrika) During The Covid 19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: Tourism can attract tourists with various factors and the efforts made by the manager of the tourist attraction. The research objective was to determine the quality of service, creativity, promotional media whether or not to influence visitor satisfaction. West Bandung has many interesting and creative tourist attractions, one of which is the Farm house and The Great Asia Afrika. Bandung tourist attractions in Indonesia are in great demand by tourists, before the COVID-19 pandemic, these 19 attractions reached 1,000 visitors and were packed with traffic jams. The existence of the Covid 19 pandemic has greatly affected the entire tourism sector, but researchers conducted research on the 3 X variables on visitor satisfaction during the Covid 19 pandemic. The research methods used were mixed method, quantitative descriptive and qualitative. The research sample used the incidental technique, visitors who were at the time of the study who were respondents were 42 people. The results showed that all X variables proved valid, namely X1, X2, X3 exceeding the R table value of 0.3044. The results of the validity test of the 25 statements used in the study. In variable Y there are 4 statements, the results of the validity test state that the validity exceeds the R table value of 0.3044. the value of the coefficient of determination or R Square of 0.745. that is, the variable under study explains 74.5% and the remaining 25.5% is explained by other variables not examined in this study. The significance value of the T test on service quality is $0.017 < 0.05$, which means that service quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. The significance value of the T test for Creativity is $0.279 > 0.05$, which means that creativity does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction. And the Promotion Media variable has a significance value of $0.00 < 0.005$ which means that the Promotion Media has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. So it can be concluded that a large and significant influence in this study is service quality on customer satisfaction, media promotion on customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, creativity does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction. In the Covid 19 pandemic, the level of visits has indeed decreased, but it still attracts tourists to visit the Farm House and The Great Asia Afrika. The profiles of these attractions are views and photo spots with nuances of Europe, Japan, Korea, Africa, India and Indonesia. Suggestions for future researchers can see from other indicators of customer satisfaction.

KEYWORD: Service Quality, Creativity, Promotion Media, Toward Visitor Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Many people have done traveling activities during the Covid 19 pandemic. People feel bored and tired of being at home, so many of them have toured activities. Some tourist destinations that are being recognized by the public, one of which is West Bandung or Lembang. Pradana (2020), the first day of the long holiday in October 2020, the tourist area of Lembang, West Bandung Regency, began to be crowded with tourists from various regions since the morning. The traffic flow was observed to be very smooth. Crowds of tourists line the entrance to tourist attractions, one of which is The Great Asia Afrika.

The tourism sector needs to rise from the covid 19 pandemic, therefore it is necessary to make every effort to increase tourism in Indonesia. Promotion media and service quality also need to be improved to encourage people to travel safely, comfortably and happily.

Susyanti and Latianingsih (2014: 65 - 66), the tourism sector is a very important source of foreign exchange and is able to make a significant contribution to development. Conventional tourism products are starting to be abandoned and tourists turn to tourism products that value the environment, nature, culture and special attractions. Tourist satisfaction no longer relies on natural beauty and the completeness of tourist facilities but also on the flexibility and intensity of interactions with the environment and local communities.

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According to Mardiana (2020), the latest tour in West Bandung which is on trial since November 22, 2019 and will be soft launching on December 5, 2019. The Great Asia Afrika Lembang carries the theme of cultural education tourism, seeing the complete cultural diversity in seven countries in Asia and Africa. with traditional culinary. According to mytrip.123.(2020), a farm house is one of the tourist attractions in Bandung which is on the rise. This tour presents an atmosphere of European-style farms, plantation areas and dwarf villages. This makes Farm House a very attractive tourist spot for children in Bandung.

The closest destinations to the capital city of Jakarta are tourist destinations for vacation and get rid of boredom, such as Bandung and Bogor. Bandung tourism is in demand by tourists because it is close to other tourist destinations, so they can travel to several destination locations. However, to be known and to attract the attention of tourists or visitors, promotional media is needed. In this millennial era, the fastest promotion is using digital marketing.

Travel activities need some support, because tourists who travel to feel happy, comfortable, happy, and safe. So several things are needed that support the desires of tourists. The quality of service from tourist destinations is considered by visitors. Because the quality of service provided will be an impression and present a comfortable atmosphere for visitors. In addition, there are promotional media that offer several attractive destinations and packages that are of interest to visitors. However, there are several tourist destinations that are not compatible with those promoted in online media. Because of these problems, we wanted to know the quality of service and the promotional media used. This also goes hand in hand with the creativity that is presented and packaged by the manager of the tourist destination. So it is necessary to know whether there is an influence between service quality, creativity, and promotional media. So that it can foster visitor satisfaction at the tourist destinations provided.

These research components are used to find out the details of the response of visitors who come to visited tourist destinations. The problem is that there is a promotional media that does not match the reality in tourist destinations. The quality of services provided to visitors is not known whether it can impress visitors or not, due to changes in circumstances and new habits that must be implemented. Due to the covid 19 pandemic, various sectors have experienced new habit changes. There are still a number of tourist destinations that have not implemented new health protocols and habits, so the quality of services provided is not optimal. Therefore, it is necessary to know the quality of service provided by the currently hit destinations in Bandung.

Sangkaeng (2015: 1090) states that the quality of tourism services is directly dependent on hospitality, attractiveness of the location, local products and others. The dimensions of tourism service quality include security, comfort, atmosphere, privacy, respect, friendliness, competence, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, courtesy and honesty. The problem faced by the tourism sector in Indonesia is that each region competes with each other to increase the attractiveness of destinations, so that the value or tourist attraction will greatly affect the level of tourist visits.

Bandung Indonesia has several creative and attractive tourist attractions. Tourist attractions in Bandung are a tourist destination for capturing photos and uploading them to social media.

According to Gunelius (2011) there are four elements that are used as a variable for the success of social media marketing: 1) Content Creation, interesting content or content that will become the basis for conducting social media marketing. Content must be made as attractive as possible but still represent the personality of a business so that consumers trust more. 2) Content Sharing, sharing content with social communities can help expand a business network and expand the online audience. By sharing content, sales will indirectly occur as the content is spread. 3) Connecting, social networking allows a person to meet more people who have the same interests. An extensive network can build relationships that can generate more business. Honest and careful communication must be considered when doing social networking. 4) Community Building, the social web is a large online community of individuals where there is interaction between people who live around the world using technology. Building community on the internet can happen accidentally as long as you have common interests.

Social media that attracts visitors' interest will bring tourists to tourist sites. Therefore, it will raise visitor satisfaction about the tourist objects that have been visited. Visitor satisfaction is the main thing expected by tourism actors and tourism destination organizers. Visitors who are satisfied with the tourism activities carried out at tourist destination locations. Surely you will be impressed and tell your family, friends, and updates on social media. Because it cannot be denied, tourism in the millennial generation and 2000s has used digital media. Harahap (2014: 5) states that satisfaction is a response to behavior shown by customers by comparing the performance or perceived results with expectations. If the perceived results are below expectations, then the customer will be disappointed, less satisfied or even dissatisfied, but on the contrary, if it is in accordance with the expectations, the customer will be satisfied and if the performance exceeds expectations, the customer will be very satisfied

II. METHODOLOGY

The research methods used were mixed method, quantitative descriptive and qualitative. The research sample used the incidental technique, visitors who were at the time of the study who were respondents were 42 people. Data collection techniques using questionnaires, interviews, and observations. The researcher triangulated the data by interviewing several main respondents, namely managers and visitors.

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III. RESEARCH RESULT

A. Tourism Profile of West Bandung

West Bandung tourism which is widely known to the public in 2019 - now, namely The Great Asia Afrika and Farm House. This tourist location has a modern feel and displays a European style. Farm House has been operating longer than The Great Asia Afrika. This tourist location is in the Lembang area, West Bandung.

The farm house is located on Jl.Raya Lembang No.108, Gudangkahuripan, Lembang, West Bandung Regency, West Java. This tourist location is close to The Great Asia Afrika. Based on information from the manager that the 2 tourist objects are managed by the same management. Farm house attractions offer various destinations for children, adolescents and adults. The farm house ticket price is IDR 30,000, parking vehicles are charged IDR 5,000 for motorbikes and IDR 10,000 for cars. Visitors can exchange tickets purchased for cold fresh milk, there are 3 flavors of milk, namely original, strawberry, and chocolate. The tourist destinations offered at Farm House attractions are: European houses and costume rental, education on feeding animals, hobbit houses, love locks, photos with animals, photo spots, shopping tours.

The Great Asia Afrika is located opposite the farm house, so visitors choose 2 nearby tourist sites in West Bandung. This tourist location is on Jl. Raya Lembang - Bandung No.71, Gudangkahuripan, Lembang, West Bandung Regency, West Java. Bandung tourism is not only popular with the exoticism of Nature Tourism in Bandung, but now there are many contemporary tourist attractions that are fresher and can accommodate all recreational needs for all age groups, not only limited to tourist attractions for the elderly, but also very friendly as a tourist spot for children in Bandung and teenagers. The tours offered are photo spots, culinary spots, shopping, entertainment, games that represent the characteristics of 7 countries from 2 continents of Asia and Africa in one location. The ticket price offered from this destination is IDR 50,000. Motorcycle parking fees are IDR 5,000 and car parking IDR 10,000. The tourist destinations offered at The Great Asia Afrika tourist attraction, namely: Jaipurs India's Pink City, typical Japanese villages, African homes, Korean nuances, Thai nuances, Indonesian nuances, Dutch flower gardens, exchange of tickets for food or drinks, dino land, tours shopping and culinary tours.

In the research of Stolarick, et.al (2010: 238), Prince Edward County is an extraordinary example of a rural community that has utilized its natural resources with a focus on the creative economy including gastronomy, enology, culture and heritage, and visual arts to create not only a desired tourist destination but also a dynamic regional economic development.

As with previous research, that creativity is needed to improve the creative economy and present culture. Creative tourism objects can bring tourists to visit and become tourist attractions.

B. Characteristics of Respondents

That 42 respondents who became tourist visitors in West Bandung (The Great Asia Afrika and Farm House), the highest gender was dominated by women at 58.1% and men 41.9%. Women are more dominant in liking photo tourism objects and scenery that can be used as photo objects. Because the photos obtained will be uploaded to social media.

West Bandung tourist visitors (The Great Asia Afrika and Farm House) reside at 37.2% in Bekasi, 30.2% in Bandung, 23.3% come from Jakarta. The three origin of tourists are the closest areas to West Bandung, so tourists live in Bekasi, Bandung and Jakarta. People in these areas will tend to travel to Bandung or Bogor, because they are the closest areas to where they live.

Respondents of tourist visitors in West Bandung (The Great Asia Afrika and Farm House) based on age were dominated by 17-25 years or late adolescents as much as 44.2%. The second highest number of visitors was 36 - 45 years or late adults as much as 39.5%. Furthermore, the age of 26 - 35 years as much as 16.3%. Based on the results of the research, most respondents who carry out tourism activities in West Bandung are aged 17-25 years, namely adolescents and late teens. Most respondents were private employees whose age was in this range. Because at this age it is dominant to do travel activities, gather with friends or family, update photos on social media, and relieve fatigue after work.

On a tour in West Bandung (The Great Asia Afrika and Farm House). Dominated by private employees 32.6%, followed by visitors with student or student criteria as much as 30.2%. Because this tourist location has beautiful nature and cool air, making it suitable for visitors who work to relieve fatigue.

C. Research Results Service Quality, Creativity and Promotion Media Toward Visitor Satisfaction

Richards (2013:2), a model is proposed that depicts the transformation of culture and creativity in cities from a model of patronage and subsidy towards their definition as economic sectors and increasingly towards 'Culture 3.0', which exhibits increasing co-creation of experiences and the rise of embedded creativity and everyday creativity as attractions.

Variable X is a variable that affects visitor satisfaction or variable Y. Variable X1 is the quality of service provided by the tourist attraction of West Bandung (The Great Asia Afrika and Farm House). The X2 variable is the creativity presented by the West Bandung tourist attraction (The Great Asia Afrika and Farm House). Variable X3 is the promotional media used by the tourist attraction.

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Table 4.1. Validity test table

	NILAI KORELASI
X1.1	.820
X1.2	.772
X1.3	.801
X1.4	.840
X1.5	.792
X1.6	.473
X1.7	.797
X1.8	.791
X1.9	.861
X1.10	.853
X1.11	.777
X1.12	.860
X1.13	.846
X2.1	.560
X2.2	.814
X2.3	.769
X2.4	.789
X2.5	.667
X2.6	.759
X2.7	.800
X2.8	.755
X3.1	.586
X3.2	.596
X3.3	.650
X3.4	.546
JUMLAH	1.000

Based on the output above, the correlation value has exceeded the R table value of 0.3044. This means that the X data is valid. All X variables are proven valid, namely X1, X2, X3 exceeding the R table value of 0.3044. The results of the validity test of the 25 statements used in the study.

Variable Y is visitor satisfaction at tourist attractions in West Bandung (The Great Asia Africa and Farm House). The validity of the statements contained in the variable Y questionnaire is tested. The following are the results of the validity test:

Table 4.2. Validity test Y Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	JUMLAH_Y
Y1	1.000	.641	.630	.390	.808
Y2	.641	1.000	.860	.463	.916
Y3	.630	.860	1.000	.402	.891
Y4	.390	.463	.402	1.000	.665
JUMLAH_Y	.808	.916	.891	.665	1.000

Based on the output above, the correlation value has exceeded the R table value of 0.3044. This means that the X statement on the questionnaire is valid. In variable Y there are 4 statements, the results of the validity test state that the validity exceeds the R table value of 0.3044.

Test reliability is the level of consistency of a test, namely the extent to which a test can be trusted to be true in a study. In the X and Y variables test for the reliability test values as follows:

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Table 4.3. Reliability Test X

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.761	.969	26

Cronbach's Alpha value has exceeded 0.60, meaning that the statement on variable Y is reliable. Based on the reliability test, it states that all statements consisting of 25 items in the questionnaire are declared reliable.

Test the reliability of the variable Y.

Table 4.4. Reliability Test Y

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.823	.909	5

Cronbach's Alpha value has exceeded 0.60, meaning that the statement on variable Y is reliable. Based on the reliability test, it states that all statements consisting of 4 items in the variable Y questionnaire are declared reliable.

Table 4.5. Mean Variable Creativity (X2)

Statistics

	X2.1	X2.2	X2.3	X2.4	X2.5	X2.6	X2.7	X2.8
Valid N	42	42	42	42	42	42	42	42
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	4.0000	4.0714	3.9048	3.9524	4.0238	4.0238	4.0238	3.9048
Median	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
Sum	168.00	171.00	164.00	166.00	169.00	169.00	169.00	164.00

Statistical results mean, median and mean of variable X2 or creativity. There is the highest indicator value of 4.0714, namely statements of quality, diverse and competitive natural resource indicators.

Statistical results mean, median and mean of variable X3 or promotional media.

Table 4.6. Mean Variable promotional media (X3)

Statistics

	X3.1	X3.2	X3.3	X3.4
Valid N	42	42	42	42
Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	4.0238	4.1190	4.0952	4.0476
Median	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
Sum	169.00	173.00	172.00	170.00

The highest mean is found in the Content Sharing indicator in the statement of tourist attraction information obtained from friends status updates on social media of 4.1190.

The results of research by Indika and Jovita (2017: 30), Instagram social media show that the communication of photos that are packaged creatively is an important factor in attracting consumers' attention to tourist destinations. The Instagram social media

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application that features sharing of photos or images has proven to have a strong correlation in influencing consumer buying interest.

Statistical results mean, median and mean of variable Y (Visitor Satisfaction).

Table 4.7. Mean Variable Visitor Satisfaction(Y) Statistics

	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
N Valid	42	42	42	42
Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.8095	4.0000	4.1429	4.0476
Median	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
Sum	160.00	168.00	174.00	170.00

Based on the results of the calculation of the SPSs regarding the visitor satisfaction variable (Y), the lowest mean value at Y1 is 3.8095, which is a statement about the information obtained about the tourist attraction in accordance with the expected reality. The highest mean is at Y3 of 4.1429 regarding recommending tourist objects to others.

KoefisienDeterminasi (R Square)

Table 4.8. KoefisienDeterminasi Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.863 ^a	.745	.725	.38857	2.358

a. Predictors: (Constant), Media Promotion, Creativity, Service Quality

b. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction

Based on the output above, it is known that the coefficient of determination or R Square is 0.745.that is, the variable under study explains 74.5% and the remaining 25.5% is explained by other variables not examined in this study.The joint effect on these 4 variables is 74.5%.

Simultaneous Test (Test F)

From the output above, it is known that the significance value in the F test is 0.00.because Sig.0.00 <0.05, then Service Quality (X1), Creativity (X2), and Media Promotion (X3) affect Customer Satisfaction (Y).So that the results of this study can be stated that 3 variables X and 1 variable Y influence each other.

Table 4.9. Simultaneous Test

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.746	3	5.582	36.969	.000b
	Residual	5.738	38	.151		
	Total	22.483	41			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Media Promotion, Creativity, Service Quality						

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Partial Test (T Test)

Table 4.10. Partial Test

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.092	.383		.240	.812
Service Quality	.345	.138	.340	2.507	.017
Creativity	.132	.120	.134	1.098	.279
Media Promotion	.491	.099	.514	4.961	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer satisfaction

From the output above, it can be seen that the significance value of the T test on service quality is 0.017 <0.05, which means that service quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. The significance value of the T test for Creativity is 0.279 > 0.05, which means that creativity does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction. And the Promotion Media variable has a significance value of 0.00 <0.005 which means that the Promotion Media has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. So it can be concluded that a large and significant influence in this study is service quality on customer satisfaction, promotional media on customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, creativity does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion of this study, the three independent variables affect the dependent variable. Service quality is valued at 0.017 <0.05, meaning that service quality has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. Creativity is 0.279 > 0.05, which means that creativity has no significant effect on customer satisfaction. And the Promotion Media variable has a significance value of 0.00 <0.005 which means that the Promotion Media has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction. So it can be concluded that a large and significant influence in this study is service quality on customer satisfaction, media promotion on customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, creativity does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction. Based on the 4 research variables, there are results 0.00 <0.05, then Service Quality (X1), Creativity (X2), and Media Promotion (X3) have an effect on Customer Satisfaction (Y). So that the results of this study can be stated that 3 variables X and 1 variable Y influence each other. The strong influence between the variables of service quality and promotional media has a very strong influence on customer satisfaction. Because today's visitors come to tourist objects to get good photos, so they can be uploaded to social media such as Instagram, Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube. The next researcher can examine the effect of other indicators on customer satisfaction.

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